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12 **Concentration dependent effects of human Cometin on spiral**
13 **ganglion neuron survival and neurite outgrowth**

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35 **Concentration dependent effects of human Cometin on spiral ganglion neuron survival and neurite**
36 **outgrowth**

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Abstract

Introduction: Neurotrophic factors are widely known for their protective effect on spiral ganglion neurons (SGN) and the protection of these neurons is of great importance to optimize Cochlear Implants, which directly stimulate SGN in deaf patients. Previous studies have identified Cometin - also known as Meteorin-like - to be neuroprotective and beneficial for metabolic disorders. The aim of our study was to investigate the effects of different concentrations of recombinant human Cometin (hCometin) on SGN in regard to neuroprotection and neurite outgrowth and to evaluate its neurite guidance potential using a neurite outgrowth chamber.

Methods: Human Cometin was initially tested in two separate dosing experiments: 5, 10, and 15 µg/ml (medium dose group) and 10, 25, and 50 µg/ml (high dose group). The hCometin was added to dissociated neonatal murine SGN. The number, morphology, and neurite length of SGN treated with hCometin were compared to untreated (negative control, NC) and brain-derived neurotrophic factor treated (50 ng/ml) (positive control, PC) cells. Subsequently, to investigate a potential effect on neurite guidance, 10 µg/ml hCometin was delivered via osmotic pumps to neonatal murine spiral ganglion explants (SGE) cultured in a neurite outgrowth chamber to experimentally mimic the scala tympani and the Rosenthal's canal. The amount of pump-released hCometin was measured by Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay and neurite growth was quantified and compared to a Cometin-free NC.

Results: All medium dose group concentrations of hCometin resulted in significant neuronal protection, whereas high dose group concentrations (25 and 50 µg/ml) were neurotoxic. The medium doses significantly increased the number of monopolar neurons compared to NC, and 10 and 15 µg/ml hCometin increased the number of neurons with a physiological bipolar morphology to an even greater extent than BDNF. For neurite length, 5 and 10 µg/ml hCometin had the greatest effect, which was comparable with the BDNF-PC. The osmotic-pump based delivery of 10 µg/ml hCometin to SGE had no or an adverse effect on the number, extent, or orientation of outgrowing neurites in the culture set up used.

Conclusion: A concentration of 10 µg/ml hCometin significantly protects dissociated SGN from degeneration and significantly increases the outgrowth of neurites, which is favourable in view of induced neurite outgrowth towards cochlear electrode arrays for future optimisation of the nerve-electrode-interface. The study failed to detect a guided neurite outgrowth by pump-based drug release, which may be due to the experimental set up, which could be improved in future studies.

1. Introduction

Spiral ganglion neurons (SGN) are the primary auditory neurons, connecting the cochlear hair cells and the second-order sensory neurons located in the cochlear nucleus. Degeneration of SGN is linked to many types of hearing disorders including age-related, noise-induced, or drug-induced hearing loss. Since SGN are the target cells of the electrical stimulation mediated by cochlear implants (CI), the benefit patients gain by cochlear implantation depends, amongst other issues, on the number of residual healthy SGN (1-3). Therefore, protecting SGN has important clinical significance. Studies suggest that the application of exogenous neurotrophic factors can effectively rescue SGN and promote neurite outgrowth. Among them, brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) (4-7), glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF) (3, 8), and neurotrophin-3 (NT-3) (9, 10) have been intensively investigated (11, 12). In order to establish a clinically applicable neurotrophic therapy for the cochlear, tremendous efforts have been made for decades to find the optimal compound, its biologically relevant but safe concentration, and a most effective but atraumatic application method. Until now, no neurotrophic factor is used in routine clinical CI care. One reason for this is the perilymph of the cochlea communicating directly with the cerebrospinal fluid, which allows some factors to enter the cerebrospinal fluid. However, neurotrophic factors are mainly applied via systemic administration in clinic, and the impact of neurotrophic factors that enters the cerebrospinal fluid through perilymph is largely unknown. Secondly, animal experiments showed that the efficacy of investigated neurotrophic factors will gradually be lost after drug withdrawal (6, 13). Therefore, it is necessary to explore additional, possibly more effective factors with neuroprotective and neurotogenic effects. Cometin, which is also known as Meteorin-like is such a possible neurotrophic factor. Its gene is located on mouse chromosome 11qE2 and human chromosome 17q25.3 (14, 15). Cometin is a well-conserved secreted protein which exhibits approximately 77 % amino acid sequence homology between the human and murine Cometin genes (16). In mice, Cometin plays a crucial role in development as observed by its selective expression in the floor plate throughout the central nervous system from E9.5, whilst from E13.5 it can be detected in sensory ganglia and the inner ear. These latter tissues align with expression of Cometin in the adult, which is more

restricted to peripheral cell populations with varying function (15, 17-20). In humans, Cometin is expressed in subcutaneous white adipose tissue, liver, spleen, muscle, and heart (14). Accordingly, Cometin links host-adaptive responses to the regulation of energy homeostasis and tissue inflammation and has therapeutic potential for metabolic and inflammatory diseases (21). Watanabe et al. reported that Cometin is a latent process gene involved in cellular function and neurite extension (22). Jørgensen et al. reported that Cometin promotes neurite outgrowth and neuroblast migration *in vitro*, and it supports SGN survival and electrical responsiveness *in vivo* (15). Notably, the latter study was limited to an ototoxic drug-induced hearing loss model, and the mechanism of neuroprotective action remains to be further investigated.

In a previous study we observed that recombinant human Cometin has a significantly larger potential to prevent rat SGN from degeneration than murine Cometin (23). The neuroprotective effect of the highest tested concentration of 10 µg/ml human Cometin was as good as that of human BDNF, which was used as a positive control. In the present study, we compared the effects of higher concentrations of human Cometin on dissociated rat SGN survival, morphology, and neurite outgrowth. Additionally, we explored the effect of osmotic pump-based delivery of human Cometin on spiral ganglion explants (SGE) to evaluate neurite outgrowth and guidance.

2. Method and material

Previously, we have reported a significant neuroprotective effect of 10 µg/ml recombinant human Cometin (hCometin) on dissociated SGN (23). To further explore the dose range over which this neuroprotective effect occurs, in the present study we examined two higher ranges of hCometin concentrations: 5, 10, and 15 µg/ml (middle dose group) and 10, 25, and 50 µg/ml (high dose group). Both sets of concentrations were tested separately on dissociated SGN for their effect on neuronal survival and morphology and, in the case of the middle dose group concentrations, additionally for length of neurite outgrowth. In a subsequent experimental set-up, spiral ganglion explants (SGE) were maintained in a Neurite Outgrowth Chamber (NOC) and treated with 10 µg/ml hCometin delivered via an osmotic pump to investigate potential effects on neurite guidance.

2.1 Spiral ganglion (SG) preparation

Neonatal Sprague-Dawley rats (2-4 days old) from an in-house colony were used for SG (spiral ganglion) preparation in accordance with the German “Law on protecting animals” and the European Communities Council Directive 86/609/EEC for the protection of animals used for experimental purposes. All experiments were registered with the local authorities.

After rapid decapitation, the skin and skull were opened along the sagittal plane and the brain was removed. The back half of the skull, which includes the temporal bones, was cut ventrally along the midline. The temporal bones were removed and transferred into a Petri dish (60 x 15 mm; BD Falcon, Sparks, USA) with ice-cold $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ -free D-phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (Invitrogen, Karlsruhe, Germany). The SG was dissected under microscopic control (Leica KL 1500 LCD; Leica, Wetzlar, Germany). The temporal bone was opened, the cochlea identified and the bony cochlear capsule carefully removed. The membranous labyrinth of the cochlea was separated and transferred to another Petri dish with ice-cold PBS. Under higher magnification, the membranous capsule was removed and the stria vascularis, the Organ of Corti and the SG were detached from the modiolus. Finally, the SG was separated from the stria vascularis and Organ of Corti and stored in ice-cold $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ -free Hank’s balanced salt solution (HBSS) (Gibco Invitrogen, Karlsruhe, Germany).

2.2 Dissociated SGN culture

2.2.1 SGN dissociation

The SG were enzymatically dissociated using 0.1 % trypsin (Biochrom, Berlin, Germany) and 0.01 % DNase I (Roche, Mannheim, Germany), followed by mechanical dissociation, where the cells of the spiral ganglion (SGC) were triturated until no cell clusters were visible in the suspension. For details, please see Schwieger et al. (5). After determining the cell number in a Neubauer chamber (BRAND GmbH, Wertheim, Germany) using the trypan blue (Sigma Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) exclusion test, the SGC suspension was diluted to a final concentration of 1×10^4 cells/50 µl ($\pm 20 \times 10^4$ cells/ml) with culture medium (see below).

2.2.2 SGN cultivation

Poly-D/L-ornithine (0.1 mg/ml, Sigma Aldrich) and laminin (0.01 mg/ml Naturel Mouse Laminin; Invitrogen) coated wells of a 96-multiwell culture plate (Nunc A/S, Roskilde, Denmark) were used for cell seeding. Panserin 401 (Pan Biotech, Passau, Germany) supplemented with insulin (8.7 µg/ml; Biochrom), penicillin (30 U/ml; Biochrom), glucose (0.15 %; B. Braun Melsungen), PBS (0.172 mg/ml; Gibco by life-technologies), HEPES-buffer solution (23.43 µM; Invitrogen) and N2-supplement (0.1 µl/ml; Invitrogen) was applied as a starvation culture medium (SGC-medium). 1×10^4 SGC suspended in 50 µl medium were seeded into each well. Culture was

performed in a humidified (95 %) atmosphere of 5 % CO₂ at 37 °C. Human Cometin in concentrations of 5, 10, 15, 25 and 50 µg/ml were added to the SGC culture at time of seeding. High dose group experiments (10, 25, 50 µg/ml) were performed with 200 µl volume per well to avoid the concentration of nutrients in the medium being too low due to dilution by the high volume of added hCometin. The experiments for the medium dose group of hCometin (5, 10, 15 µg/ml) were performed with 100 µl per well as standardly used for neuroprotection assays. To equalize all conditions in respect of the added factor volume and to ensure the comparability, factors were diluted in a proportional amount of PBS. SGC cultivated in control media with addition of 50 ng/ml BDNF (human recombinant BDNF, from E. coli; Invitrogen), which has previously been shown to induce optimal SGN survival (8), served as positive control. Negative control contained no additional BDNF. Fixation was performed with 1:1 acetone/methanol solution after 4 hours for wells used to determine the seeding density of SGN, and after 48 hours of cultivation for experimental group wells.

2.2.3 Immunocytochemistry (ICC) and SGN analysis

ICC: To identify the neurons in the SGC culture, SGN were specifically labelled by immunocytochemistry using mouse monoclonal neurofilament-200 kDa primary antibody (1:500, #NCL-L-NF200-N52; Novacastra™ LeicaBiosystems, Wetzlar, Germany) and stained with the Vectastain® Elite® ABC kit (#PK-6100, Vector Laboratories, California, United States) followed by peroxidase substrate kit (DAB, #SK-4100; Vector Laboratories, California, United States).

SGN survival: The number of surviving SGN was determined microscopically. SGN showing a positive immunostaining and a neurite length three times the length of the somas' diameter were defined as surviving neurons and counted per well for determination of SGN number. Additionally, the survival rate was calculated by setting the number of counted surviving neurons in a ratio with the number of neurons observed initially 4 hours after seeding, providing the survival rate as percentage of the seeding control.

Morphology: For neuronal morphology, the SGN were classified into the following groups: monopolar, bipolar, multipolar, pseudomonopolar and no neurites. Neurons that could not be clearly identified or cells in clusters were not counted (24). For better comparability, additionally the percentages of the different neuronal morphologies were calculated from the total number of counted neurons per well.

Neurite length: For the analysis of SGN neurite length, five fields of view were microscopically visualised (Olympus CKX 41 microscope with Olympus XC30 digital colour camera, Hamburg, Germany) to assess the whole well. The 15 longest neurites of these five fields of view (3 neurites/field) were measured using the polygon function of the image analysis program (ImageJ/FIJI). If one cell presented several neurites, the longest neurite was analysed. For wells with less than 15 neurons in total, the longest neurite of every neuron was measured.

2.3 Spiral ganglion explant (SGE) culture

2.3.1 Neurite outgrowth chamber (NOC)

For analysis of possible neurite attraction, SGE were cultivated in a custom-made chamber (25) 3D printed out of polylactic acid (PLA, Innofil3D BV, Emmen, The Netherlands). This was connected to a mini-osmotic pump (Alzet® osmotic pumps, model 2002 (Durect Corporation, Cupertino, CA, USA)), with an infusion rate of 0.5 µl/h and a pump volume of 200 µl to provide up to two weeks of localized and continuous drug delivery. The NOC design is based on the distance that occurs between SG and cochlear implant electrodes in human cochleae with the scale increased by fivefold to allow for sufficient medium supply, formation of a diffusion gradient, and manipulation for tissue seeding. The chambers consist of two compartments: adhesion area of SGE, and factor release area, where the tube, which is connected to the osmotic pump, is positioned. A central channel connects both compartments and allows factor diffusion to the SGE. Based on the pump characteristics, it was calculated that a desired concentration of 10 µg/ml hCometin in the medium is reached within 30 hours after connection to the NOC, when a hCometin concentration of 100 µg/ml is released. Therefore, pumps were filled with artificial perilymph (AP (3), including human serum albumin (Sigma Aldrich)) with or without (NC) addition of 100 µg/ml hCometin. The pumps were filled as recommended by the manufacturer and were connected to an AP (NC) or AP + hCometin filled 3 cm long catheter (ALZET® Rat Femoral Catheter; Durect Corporation, Cupertino, CA, USA; No.: 0007720).

2.3.2 SGE cultivation in NOC

The glass slide bottom of the NOCs were poly-D/L-ornithine and laminin coated as described for the dissociated SGC above to support cell adhesion and growth. NOC were prefilled with 150 µl/NOC SGC-medium (see above) containing 10 % serum (fetal calf serum, Invitrogen) for SGE seeding. Prepared SG were cut in five equal parts and positioned from apex to base in front of the connection channel in the NOC, with the lateral side facing the pump

inlet. To improve adhesion of the SGE after positioning, cells were precultivated for 24 hours in the presence of serum and without the pumps. Culture was performed in a humidified (95 %) atmosphere of 5 % CO₂ at 37 °C. The following day, SGE within the NOC were examined for proper adhesion and cell growth before being transferred to a modified 6-well plate and connected either to a mini-osmotic pump containing 100 µg/ml hCometin in AP or pure AP (NC). To analyse the direct effect of hCometin compared to NC, medium was changed to 150 µl serum-free starvation medium before starting the co-culture with the pumps. Cultivation was performed for 5 days under the same conditions as indicated above. Subsequently the SGE were fixed with 4 % PFA (paraformaldehyde). Since pumps release factors for two weeks, one NOC experiment was performed in the first week and another one with new NOC and SGE in the second week. In total, six independent sets of experiments with hCometin and NC were performed with five SGE pieces per NOC.

2.3.3 ICC and SGE analysis in NOC

ICC and neurite outgrowth analysis was performed as previously described in detail (25). In each NOC, three to five SGE remained attached to the surface after the five-day cultivation, fixation, and staining and were available for analysis. The counting and measurement of neurite number, length, and orientation were performed with FIJI on images taken using a fluorescence microscope (Keyence BioRevo BZ-9000E) and corresponding software (BZ-II Viewer and BZ-II Analyzer).

ICC: SGN were specifically labelled by immunocytochemistry using chicken polyclonal neurofilament - 200 kDa primary antibody (ab4680; Abcam, Cambridge, United Kingdom; host species: chicken, diluted 1:10,000 in blocking solution) and goat anti-chicken DyLight 488 secondary antibody (ab96947; Abcam, Cambridge, UK; diluted 1:200 in blocking solution) in combination with DAPI (AppliChem GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany; 1:10).

Analysis: The explant area was measured manually (Fig. 1a) to report the neurite number in relation to the explant size. The number of neurites regenerated from each SGE was determined by manual counting (Fig. 1b). For each of the three to five explant pieces per NOC, the numbers were determined separately. The neurite number is given as number per SGE and as number per 1 µm² of the explant. For the analysis of the SGN neurite length, the 10 longest regenerated neurites were measured per SGE (Fig. 1c). The area covered by regenerated neurites was determined by marking the outline of the outgrown neurites and subtracting the respective SGE area. The neurite orientation in relation to the pump was determined by manually counting the number of neurites growing towards the connection channel (+) or away from it (-). Additionally, the area of regenerated neurites directed towards or away from the connecting channel was determined by drawing a centered line through the explant. This marked the area facing either towards (Fig. 1d) or away (Fig. 1e) from the pump. By addition of these areas, the overall neurite coverage area named above was calculated. The collected numbers and areas for neurite orientation were calculated as percentage of the two directions for statistical assessment.

2.3.4 hCometin detection

To evaluate the pump-based release of hCometin in the NOC experiments over time, sample concentrations were measured by ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) detection (Human Meteorin-like/METRNL DuoSet ELISA (DY7867-05), DuoSet Ancillary Reagent Kit 2 (DY008); both R&D Systems). ELISA was performed according to the manufacturer's instructions. The experimental set up allowed a collection of pump-released hCometin at different time points (Fig. 2).

Continuous drug-release from the filled pumps is classically achieved via an osmotic pressure difference between an internal compartment within the pumps and the tissue environment. This pressure had to be initiated by preincubating the pumps in saline for one day until they were 'primed' and the pre-determined flow rate was attained. The primed pumps were then kept immersed in PBS and connected to a batch of NOCs for the first five days of drug release (day 1-5) before being disconnected from the NOCs on days 6 and 7 to allow for preparation of the second batch of NOCs containing fresh SGE. These were connected to the pumps for another five days (day 8-12) before being disconnected for the two final days (day 13 and 14) of the two-week pumping cycle. During connection of the pumps with a NOC, hCometin solution was released to the 150 µl SGC-medium. At the other named time points (preincubation, interim collection), the catheter of the pump was inserted in a 0.5 ml Eppendorf tube filled with 500 µl PBS to collect the released hCometin solution and to prevent its evaporation. Medium and PBS were collected at the end of the named periods and stored frozen until ELISA analysis.

In total, two sets of NOC experiments (pumping cycle I and pumping cycle II) were performed for the two-week release of drug. Each set consisted of four simultaneously cultivated NOCs, two with hCometin (Com1 and Com2) and two without (negative control, NC1 and NC2) for both the first and second week of drug release. With the exception of the first week for the first set where medium was lost due to leakage, all NOC supernatants were

collected for ELISA-analysis. Preincubation and interim collection samples were taken in both sets and additionally a sample of the Cometin solution used for pump filling in set 1 (pure I) and 2 (pure II). Beside these collected supernatants and Cometin solution, cell culture medium of inner ear tissue (SG, Organ of Corti and both connected) was collected as control to determine if detectable Cometin is produced by these cells. An overview of all samples analysed with ELISA for hCometin amount is summarized in **Table 1**.

Analysis by ELISA was performed in duplicate with dilution series of each sample after sterile filtration. Samples were measured using a BioTek microplate reader and Gen5 analysis software in accordance with the recommendations of the ELISA kit protocol by creating a standard curve (4-PL curve-fit) followed by calculation of the hCometin concentrations.

2.4 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad prism software release 5.0. All data were tested for normal distribution of the values using the D'Agostino and Pearson omnibus normality test. In the high dose group hCometin experiments with dissociated SGN, data of neuronal survival (survival rate and neurons/well) and morphology were normally distributed with equal variances (Bartlett's test) and one-way ANOVA was performed with the Bonferroni multiple comparison test to detect significant differences between groups. The medium dose group hCometin data of survival rate were normally distributed but variances differed significantly and Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's Multiple comparison test were performed. Data of neurons per well and morphology in these experiments were normally distributed with equal variance and one-way ANOVA with subsequent Bonferroni multiple comparison test were performed. The neurite length data did not pass the normality test and Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's Multiple comparison test were performed. Normal distribution of the NOC-data was heterogeneous and therefore unpaired t-test or Mann Whitney test were performed to compare the data of neurite outgrowth between groups. The mean \pm the standard deviation (SD) are reported. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1 High dose group hCometin experiments in dissociated SGN culture

3.1.1 SGN survival

Neurons treated with 25 or 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ human Cometin appeared rounded, detached and clustered (**Fig. 3**) and did not survive the cultivation time of 48 hours. No neurons showed normal cell morphology and no neurites grew out. Therefore, the neuronal number was set to 0 for analysis of these concentrations (**Fig. 4, 5**).

The mean survival rate of the NC was $3.47\% \pm$ standard deviation (SD) of 1.39% (**Fig. 4a**). Adding 50 ng/ml BDNF (positive control) significantly increased SGN survival rate to $9.92 \pm 3.27\%$ ($p < 0.01$ vs NC). The addition of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ human Cometin mediated a further significant increase in SGN survival rate to $19.69 \pm 7.49\%$ compared to the negative and the positive control (both $p < 0.001$). The number of neurons per well reflect the same results (**Fig. 4b**).

3.1.2 SGN morphology

The mean values (nominal and proportional) of SGN morphologies detected for the experimental conditions are illustrated in **Figure 5** with nominal values provided in **Table 2**. Treatment with 50 ng/ml BDNF (PC) resulted in a significantly increased number of monopolar and bipolar neurons compared to NC ($p < 0.01$), while the number of pseudomonopolar, multipolar, and neurons with no neurites did not differ significantly. Treatment with 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin resulted in significantly more monopolar, bipolar, and pseudomonopolar neurons than the NC or PC ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin also increased the number of multipolar neurons vs PC ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, the number of neurons without neurites was significantly reduced compared to PC ($p < 0.01$) when treated with 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin. There was no difference in the number of multipolar neurons and neurons with no neurites between NC and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin detectable. For both, 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin, analysis of morphology revealed only a few remaining neurons attached to the wells with no regenerated neurites. All other morphologies were graded as 0.

Viewing the data as percentage of the neuronal population (**Fig. 5f**) highlights the positive effect of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin treatment, where approximately 65% of the neuronal population showed neurite regeneration (mainly monopolar and bipolar neurons), compared to only about 35% in PC and 25% in NC.

3.2 Medium dose group hCometin experiments in dissociated SGN culture

3.2.1 SGN survival

The survival rate (**Fig. 6a**) of BDNF treated neurons ($17.64 \pm 9.63\%$) significantly differed from that of the negative control ($6.44 \pm 3.40\%$; $p < 0.05$). All three tested medium dose group hCometin concentrations significantly

protected the SGN from degeneration compared to NC, resulting in the following survival rates: 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin: $15.53 \pm 3.49\%$ ($p < 0.05$); 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin: $20.71 \pm 4.33\%$ ($p < 0.001$); 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin: $20.99 \pm 3.33\%$ ($p < 0.001$). The survival rates of hCometin treated SGN did not differ significantly among each other or from those of BDNF treated SGN. However, it should be noted that mean survival rates for 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin were noticeably higher than that for BDNF-PC.

The total number of neurons (**Fig. 6b**) in NC versus BDNF supplemented wells differed significantly (31.67 ± 15.84 neurons versus 83.75 ± 34.06 neurons; $p < 0.001$). hCometin in the medium dose group concentration significantly protected the neurons ($p < 0.001$) with a mean number of neurons as follows: 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ human Cometin: 77.83 ± 18.02 ; 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ human Cometin: 104.5 ± 27.14 ; 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ human Cometin: 106.1 ± 23.15 . No significant difference between the protective effect of BDNF or hCometin and within the three tested concentrations was observed. However, the mean number of surviving neurons for 10 and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin exceeded that of the BDNF-PC.

3.2.2 SGN morphology

Overall, the tested medium dose group hCometin concentrations (5, 10, and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) had a positive effect on the outgrowth of neurites from surviving neurons (nominal and proportional values given in **Table 3**; illustrated in **Fig. 7**). Compared to NC, the number of monopolar and bipolar neurons were significantly increased by the BDNF-control and all tested medium dose group concentrations of hCometin ($p < 0.001$; except for bipolar PC: $p < 0.01$). For monopolar SGN, no significant difference was detectable between the three medium dose group hCometin-concentrations or to PC. In the case of bipolar neurons, the highest numbers were observed in wells treated with 10 and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ vs. PC: $p < 0.01$, 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ vs. PC: $p < 0.001$; 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ vs. 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$: $p < 0.01$, 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ vs. 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$: $p < 0.001$) which did not differ significantly from each other. 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin did not increase the number of bipolar neurons compared to the PC. The only differences detected for pseudomonopolar and multipolar neurons were an increase in number after treatment with 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin, which was significant compared to both controls (pseudomonopolar: NC: $p < 0.001$, PC: $p < 0.01$; multipolar: NC: $p < 0.001$, PC: $p < 0.05$), for pseudomonopolar neurons compared to 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin ($p < 0.05$) and for multipolar neurons compared to 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Cometin ($p < 0.05$). In the case of neurons regenerating no neurites during cultivation, overall lower numbers were counted in the hCometin treated wells than in the control wells. The greatest reduction in number of neurons without neurites was induced by treatment with 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin, which was significant compared to the PC ($p < 0.05$).

The graph indicating the percentages of neurons of the whole population (**Fig. 7f**) clearly illustrates the increase of neurons with outgrown neurites, particularly of bipolar neurons, after treatment with increasing medium doses of hCometin (10 and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$: $> 50\%$) in comparison to the NC (about 30%) and PC (about 40%).

3.2.3 Neurite length

The measured mean neurite lengths of BDNF (PC), as well as 5 and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin treated neurons were significantly longer than those of neurons of the negative control (PC: $p < 0.001$, 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$: 0.001; 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$: $p < 0.01$) (**Fig. 8**). Compared to the PC and among each other, the neurite length induced by 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin did not differ significantly. Treatment with BDNF ($p < 0.01$) and 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin ($p < 0.01$) resulted in significantly longer neurites compared to 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin, while no difference was observed between 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin.

3.3. SGE culture with hCometin in NOC experiments

3.3.1 Neurite outgrowth

SGE within the NOC were examined for proper adhesion and cell growth before being connected to either a mini-osmotic pump containing 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin or pure artificial perilymph as negative control (NC) for five days of cultivation. For each NOC, three to five SGE remained for analysis after cultivation and staining procedures. The measured SGE area (**Fig. 9a**) showed no significant difference between hCometin treated tissue (SGE area/ mm^2 : 0.1586 ± 0.1668) and the NC (SGE area/ mm^2 : 0.2186 ± 0.1505). Therefore, a bias of the following results of neurite outgrowth based on differences in tissue preparation or cultured SGE size can be excluded.

For neurite outgrowth evaluation, the number of regenerated neurites per SGE and number of neurites per mm^2 SGE were measured for hCometin and compared with NC as shown in **Figure 9b, c**. Accordingly, no significant difference in the number of outgrown neurites between NC (neurites/SGE: 13.91 ± 6.14 ; neurites/ mm^2 SGE: 100.8 ± 99.59) and hCometin treatment (neurites/SGE: 13.96 ± 9.12 ; neurites/ mm^2 SGE: 141.5 ± 108.8) was observed. For neurite length analysis, the 10 longest regenerated neurites per SGE were measured. Since three to five SGE per NOC were present after cultivation, 30 to 50 neurites were measured if available, resulting in $n = 208$ (NC) and

$n = 206$ (hCometin) analysed neurites (**Fig. 9d**). The neurite length of hCometin treated SGE (0.922 ± 0.626 mm) was significantly shorter than the length of control neurites (1.659 ± 0.782 mm) ($p < 0.001$).

Finally, a connection of the neurite endings and subtraction of the corresponding SGE area gave the neurite coverage area for SGE in the two groups (**Fig. 9e**). Mean of neurite coverage area of NC was 4.682 mm² with a high standard deviation of 3.767 mm², while hCometin treatment resulted in an overall, although not significantly, smaller area covered by neurites with a mean of 3.007 ± 2.303 mm².

3.3.2 Neurite orientation

Neurite orientation in relation to the pump was determined by manually counting the number of neurites that grew out of the SGE towards (+) or away from (-) the connection channel, and by measuring the neurite coverage area for each direction. These numbers were then examined in terms of percentage distribution. Accordingly, 55 % of total neurites grew toward, and 45 % grew away from the AP-releasing pump in the NC. Similarly, 53 % of total neurites grew towards, and 47 % grew away from the pump with hCometin delivery. For neurite coverage area, the mean percentage of NC for the two directions was $52.09\% \pm 19.68\%$ (+) and $47.86\% \pm 19.68\%$ (-) respectively, while it was $52.38\% \pm 22.34\%$ (+) and $47.66\% \pm 22.36\%$ (-) for hCometin treatment. No significant differences were observed for either the number of regenerated neurites or the neurite coverage area between the hCometin treated neurons and the NC. (**Fig. 10**)

3.3.3 Cometin concentration in NOC experiments

The concentration of hCometin was detected by ELISA in the samples collected at the different time points of drug delivery to NOCs during the two pumping cycles, the hCometin solutions for pump filling, and the supernatant of cultured inner ear tissue. Results are summarized over time for hCometin treated NOCs and pure hCometin solution in **Figure 11**.

The pure hCometin solution for pump filling was calculated and set to a concentration of 100 µg/ml in an effort to obtain a theoretical concentration of 10 µg/ml in the NOCs after 30 hours of drug release. The measured amount of hCometin in the pure solutions was $31.7 (\pm 7.29$ pure I) and $25.2 (\pm 5.42$ pure II) µg/ml (**Fig. 11**). The results for the one day preincubation samples showed a very low (0.02 - 0.61 ng/ml) or undetectable concentration of hCometin. In the two days of interim collection, hCometin concentrations varied widely between time points and osmotic pumps (0.07 µg/ml I Com2 6/7 to 0.004 µg/ml I Com1 13/14). As it was the case for the pure hCometin solution samples, the concentration of interim collections was higher in the first cycle (I Com) than in the second cycle (II Com). In the NOC supernatants, a hCometin concentration of about 3.4 µg/ml (both I Com 8-12d) to 1.3 µg/ml (both II Com 8-12d) was measured after five days of delivery, whereby I Com again had higher concentrations. Within the in parallel cultured NOCs, the amount of hCometin was very similar between Com1 and Com2 of the two cycles and time points. Overall, the detected hCometin concentration decreased over time and from pumping cycle I to pumping cycle II.

It has to be noted that a small amount of hCometin (43 – 468 pg/ml) was detected in half of the NC NOC supernatants. This was not the case for the other NOC, preincubation, and interim collection samples of the NC and the analysed inner ear tissue (spiral ganglion, Organ of Corti, both connected) supernatants.

4. Discussion

We have previously shown a clear, BDNF comparable, neuroprotective effect mediated by 10 µg/ml hCometin on rat spiral ganglion neurons when tested *in vitro* over a range of 0.1 , 1 , and 10 µg/ml ([23](#)). Therefore, to help determine if neuroprotective efficacy could be further enhanced by hCometin, the current study assessed the impact of higher concentration ranges (high dose range of 10 , 25 , and 50 µg/ml and a medium dose range of 5 , 10 , and 15 µg/ml) on survival and neurite outgrowth of dissociated SGN. The tested medium concentrations (10 and 15 µg/ml) of hCometin proved to be most effective for neuroprotection and to support neuronal morphologies with regenerated neurites and even outperformed BDNF. However, both 25 and 50 µg/ml hCometin were toxic to SGN for reasons that need to be clarified in future studies.

Such effects of high growth factor concentrations on neuronal and synaptic toxicity have been reported for other molecules such as GDNF ([26-28](#)). Cometin promotes neurite outgrowth and neuroblast migration (concentration: 20 ng/ml), and mediates a neuroprotective role (concentration: 10 µg/ml) *in vivo* ([15](#), [23](#)). Nevertheless, there remains a possibility that under some conditions higher concentrations of Cometin may be harmful to cells, as demonstrated in our SGN experiments. Whilst Cometin is known to have multiple biological functions, some of which are being exploited therapeutically, its underlying physiological effects need to be better understood ([21](#), [29](#)). Accordingly, high concentrations of Cometin might recruit as yet unidentified signalling mechanisms in SGN that would be detrimental to sensory transmission in auditory pathways.

In our experiments with dissociated SGN, 10 and 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin performed optimally for neuronal survival and neurite outgrowth resulting in different SGN morphologies. These concentrations increased SGN survival in the culture by about 3.5 (medium dose group experiments) to six (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in high dose group experiments) times compared to the NC. The effect on the SGN morphology was similarly positive, with the number of monopolar neurons being about three times and bipolar neurons being about eight times higher than the NC. This positive and BDNF-surpassing effect on neuronal morphologies becomes particularly clear when considered as percentage of the neuronal population. Similar effects on morphology of cultured SGN have been reported for combinations of several trophic factors with serum (24, 30) or a defined combination of BDNF and ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF) (5), but not for a single factor as we did here for hCometin. Monopolar neurons are the morphology, which remains after retraction of the SGN dendrites as consequence of deafness. Therefore, it is assumed that the CI stimulates mainly monopolar neurons (31). In contrast, the type I SGN, which transmit the acoustic stimulus from the inner hairs cells to the brain, physiologically have a bipolar morphology (30, 32, 33). A maintenance or recovery of this latter morphology in culture, as shown here for hCometin, may indicate a potential for improving the function of the CI by reducing the distance between SGN and stimulating electrode (34). Moreover, in recent years significant progress has been made in relation to regenerating functionally active hair cells that are lost after injury. As part of this process, it will be important to support the reconnection of spiral ganglion neurons with these hair cells with e.g. a neurotogenic factor therapy, which can induce regrowth of the dendrites and regeneration of a bipolar morphology. The suitability of hCometin in this regard (connection to CI or hair cells) is supported by our findings of an increase in bipolar neurons and the length of regenerated neurites. BDNF represents a “gold standard” for SGN protection (5, 7, 35-37), although it is less effective in promoting extended neurite outgrowth or maintaining SGN morphology than other neurotrophic factors such as leukaemia inhibitory factor (LIF), CNTF or combined treatments (5, 38, 39). Our results obtained with 10 and 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin in supporting neuronal survival and morphology in both the high dose and medium dose group experiments were at least comparable to, or even superior to BDNF. Notably, in one of the four medium dose group experiments the survival rate for BDNF was outstandingly high and increased the BDNF-mean in this experimental set (see Fig. 5), albeit the same rat strain, age, preparation, and cultivation procedure was used. This could possibly have been mitigated by increasing sample size and experimental power in the medium dose group experiments. However, to help maintain the number of animals sacrificed for the experiments as low as possible and since the tendency for superiority of hCometin was clearly visible, no additional repetitions were performed.

As alluded to above, under the conditions tested here hCometin at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ optimally protected SGN from degeneration and promoted the bipolar outgrowth of neurites to a greater extent than BDNF, whilst supporting the increase of neurite length equally well. Therefore, this value was chosen as a target concentration for our NOC experiments using prolonged hCometin-release to assess effects on neurite outgrowth and possibly guidance. For this purpose, we chose to fill mini-osmotic pumps with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ human Cometin in AP to establish a chemical gradient, and to achieve in theoretical terms the optimal 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration of hCometin in the 150 μl medium of the NOC after 30 hours. This set-up and pump-based delivery strategy has been reported to increase the number and length of regenerated neurites mediated by NT3 after four days (25). In contrast, CNTF which effectively supports neurite outgrowth in SG microexplants or the dissociated SGN culture when given as a bolus (5, 40) was ineffective at inducing outgrowth in the same study. Similarly, our data show that hCometin failed to increase neurite number. Moreover, whilst all three neurotrophic factors failed to affect guidance in NOC experiments, CNTF and hCometin both reduced neurite length. A lack of effect on neurite outgrowth and neuronal survival was also detected for hCometin concentrations of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (no increase in neurite length, Fig. 8) and higher (reduction in SGN survival, Fig. 4) in our dissociated SGN culture experiments. Combined, these findings could indicate that a preservation of functional contacts between SGN and support cells such as satellite glial as maintained in the SGE could lead to a greater unwanted functional effect of the pump-delivered Cometin (41). For example, mini-pump delivery of mouse Cometin to the inner ear at a much lower concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ for two weeks protected SGN and hearing function in a deafened guinea pig model (15).

Technical limitations could also potentially explain the lack of a positive effect of hCometin on neurite outgrowth in our NOC experiments. The concentration of the pure Cometin solution used for pump filling was only 25 and 31 % of the desired 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin when assessed by specific ELISA. Similarly, hCometin concentrations of all samples of the NOC experiments were considerably lower than the targeted 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. These observations might

have occurred as a consequence of temperature linked to the simulated *in vivo* conditions, partially metabolization by cells, or freeze-thawing of the hCometin stock solution (pure II lower than pure I) and experimental samples prior to ELISA-testing. Alternatively, the reconstitution of hCometin in AP, which includes human serum albumin, could have resulted in a poorer solubility with entrapment of hCometin via aggregation formation. In addition, a deposition of hCometin to the inner wall of the pump and the catheter cannot be excluded and would reduce the amount of detectable hCometin. Although we endeavored to load osmotic pumps in accordance to the manufacturer's instructions, some volume was lost in the connecting catheter during handling for insertion into the Eppendorf tubes or during connection to the NOC. This could explain some differences between the pumps (Com1 and 2) especially during the shorter delivery time into the PBS, albeit only to a limited extent. Another possibility to consider is that neurite regeneration could have been influenced by the experimental set up (25). The pump was connected to the culture chamber by a tube which terminated approximately 10 mm from the explant in an attempt to mimic the anatomical situation *in vivo* where a drug is delivered into the scala tympani, which is separated from the SGN by the bony structures of the modiolus. The NOC dimensions are 5x larger than the anatomical distances in the human inner ear (42). Therefore, it may be that the hCometin released from the tube was simply diluted too much to enable a biological effect at the site where the SGN are positioned. However, increasing the hCometin concentration to obtain a higher concentration at the SGE may be difficult since the 100 µg/ml hCometin used in this study was already close to the solubility limit stated in the Cometin-data sheet (43). Another explanation for possible lack of efficacy on guided outgrowth might be that the 30-hour duration used to obtain the required concentration attained at the SGE was too long. Future experiments testing a more stable form and reliable release of Cometin on SGE may result in a biological effect on the outgrowing neurites in the NOC.

The very small amounts of detected hCometin in some of the NC NOC supernatants might be attributed to transfer residues from the Cometin NOCs, albeit special care was taken to avoid this during cultivation, sample collection, and ELISA testing. It is also possible that the cultured cells in these NOCs released factors that interacted with the ELISA. However, no hCometin was detected in the other, shorter incubated, tissue supernatants. Further research could shed light on this aspect.

5. Conclusion

The current data have confirmed that hCometin when provided at an optimal concentration of 10µg/ml promotes survival of dissociated SGN, manifesting as an increase in neurite outgrowth and the number of neurons with a monopolar and bipolar morphology. These observations which can be considered equivalent, or even superior to the neurotrophic factor BDNF, indicate that hCometin has a real potential to improve CI outcome by optimising the electrode nerve interface. However, we also noted that hCometin administered at higher concentrations induced signs of neurotoxicity. Our NOC experiments providing continuous infusion of hCometin to SGN explants failed to induce guided neurite outgrowth, and highlighted the need to develop an appropriate delivery method and formulation matrix that can achieve therapeutically active hCometin concentrations within the inner ear.

Statement of Ethics

The animal study was reviewed, approved and, as demanded by law, reported regularly by the local authorities of Hannover Medical School [Zentrales Tierlaboratorium, Laboratory Animal Science, Hannover Medical School; no.: 2018/215].

Conflict of Interest Statement

Authors GM and KP are employed by Hoba Therapeutics ApS. All authors gave approval to the final version of the manuscript. All authors declare that this study received funding from Hoba Therapeutics ApS. This funder had the following involvement in the study: contribution of reagents and materials, study design, human resources (JS), and preparation of the manuscript.

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Author Contributions

VS, JS, GM, and KP conceived and designed the experiments. JS performed the experiments. VS, CW, and JS analysed the data. VS and TL contributed reagents, materials, and analysis tools. VS, CW, JS, and TL wrote the paper.

Data Availability Statement

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this article. The raw data are provided by the authors without reservation. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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Reference

1. Nadol Jr JB, Burgess BJ, Gantz BJ, Coker NJ, Ketten DR, Kos I, et al. Histopathology of cochlear implants in humans. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol.* 2001;110(9):883-91.
2. Swiderski DL, Colesa DJ, Hughes AP, Raphael Y, Pfingst BE. Relationships between intrascalar tissue, neuron survival, and cochlear implant function. *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology.* 2020;21:337-52.
3. Scheper V, Paasche G, Miller JM, Warnecke A, Berkingali N, Lenarz T, et al. Effects of delayed treatment with combined GDNF and continuous electrical stimulation on spiral ganglion cell survival in deafened guinea pigs. *J Neurosci Res.* 2009;87(6):1389-99.
4. Vink HA, van Dorp WC, Thomeer HG, Versnel H, Ramekers D. Bdnf outperforms trkb agonist 7, 8, 3' -thf in preserving the auditory nerve in deafened guinea pigs. *Brain Sciences.* 2020;10(11):787.
5. Schwieger J, Warnecke A, Lenarz T, Esser K-H, Scheper V. Neuronal survival, morphology and outgrowth of spiral ganglion neurons using a defined growth factor combination. *PLoS One.* 2015;10(8):e0133680.
6. Gillespie LN, Clark GM, Bartlett PF, Marzella PL. BDNF - induced survival of auditory neurons in vivo: cessation of treatment leads to accelerated loss of survival effects. *J Neurosci Res.* 2003;71(6):785-90.
7. Leake PA, Hradek GT, Hetherington AM, Stakhovskaya O. Brain - derived neurotrophic factor promotes cochlear spiral ganglion cell survival and function in deafened, developing cats. *Journal of Comparative Neurology.* 2011;519(8):1526-45.
8. Wefstaedt P, Scheper V, Lenarz T, Stöver T. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor/glia cell line-derived neurotrophic factor survival effects on auditory neurons are not limited by dexamethasone. *Neuroreport.* 2005;16(18):2011-4.
9. Ernfors P, Li Duan M, Elshamy WM, Canlon B. Protection of auditory neurons from aminoglycoside toxicity by neurotrophin-3. *Nat Med.* 1996;2(4):463-7.
10. Wise AK, Richardson R, Hardman J, Clark G, O'leary S. Resprouting and survival of guinea pig cochlear neurons in response to the administration of the neurotrophins brain - derived neurotrophic factor and neurotrophin - 3. *Journal of Comparative Neurology.* 2005;487(2):147-65.
11. Pettingill LN, Richardson RT, Wise AK, O'Leary SJ, Shepherd RK. Neurotrophic factors and neural prostheses: potential clinical applications based upon findings in the auditory system. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng.* 2007;54(6):1138-48.
12. Leake PA, Akil O, Lang H. Neurotrophin gene therapy to promote survival of spiral ganglion neurons after deafness. *Hear Res.* 2020;394:107955.
13. Gillespie LN, Shepherd RK. Clinical application of neurotrophic factors: the potential for primary auditory neuron protection. *Eur J Neurosci.* 2005;22(9):2123-33.
14. Li ZY, Zheng SL, Wang P, Xu TY, Guan YF, Zhang YJ, et al. Subfatin is a novel adipokine and unlike Meteorin in adipose and brain expression. *CNS Neurosci Ther.* 2014;20(4):344-54.

15. Jørgensen JR, Fransson A, Fjord-Larsen L, Thompson LH, Houchins JP, Andrade N, et al. Cometin is a novel neurotrophic factor that promotes neurite outgrowth and neuroblast migration in vitro and supports survival of spiral ganglion neurons in vivo. *Exp Neurol*. 2012;233(1):172-81.
16. Zheng S-l, Li Z-y, Song J, Liu J-m, Miao C-y. Metrnl: a secreted protein with new emerging functions. *Acta Pharmacol Sin*. 2016;37(5):571-9.
17. Magdaleno S, Jensen P, Brumwell CL, Seal A, Lehman K, Asbury A, et al. BGEM: an in situ hybridization database of gene expression in the embryonic and adult mouse nervous system. *PLoS Biol*. 2006;4(4):e86.
18. Lein ES, Hawrylycz MJ, Ao N, Ayres M, Bensinger A, Bernard A, et al. Genome-wide atlas of gene expression in the adult mouse brain. *Nature*. 2007;445(7124):168-76.
19. Walker JR, Su AI, Self DW, Hogenesch JB, Lapp H, Maier R, et al. Applications of a rat multiple tissue gene expression data set. *Genome Res*. 2004;14(4):742-9.
20. Su AI, Wiltshire T, Batalov S, Lapp H, Ching KA, Block D, et al. A gene atlas of the mouse and human protein-encoding transcriptomes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 2004;101(16):6062-7.
21. Rao RR, Long JZ, White JP, Svensson KJ, Lou J, Lokurkar I, et al. Meteorin-like is a hormone that regulates immune-adipose interactions to increase beige fat thermogenesis. *Cell*. 2014;157(6):1279-91.
22. Watanabe K, Akimoto Y, Yugi K, Uda S, Chung J, Nakamuta S, et al. Latent process genes for cell differentiation are common decoders of neurite extension length. *Journal of cell science*. 2012;125(9):2198-211.
23. Schwieger J, Gao Z, Lenarz T, Munro G, Petersen KA, Scheper V. "Of Mice and Men": the relevance of Cometin and Erythropoietin origin for its effects on murine spiral ganglion neuron survival and neurite outgrowth in vitro. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*. 2023;17:1224463.
24. Whitlon DS, Grover M, Tristano J, Williams T, Coulson M. Culture conditions determine the prevalence of bipolar and monopolar neurons in cultures of dissociated spiral ganglion. *Neuroscience*. 2007;146(2):833-40.
25. Schwieger J, Frisch AS, Rau TS, Lenarz T, Hügl S, Scheper V. 3D Printed Cell Culture Chamber for Testing the Effect of Pump-Based Chronic Drug Delivery on Inner Ear Tissue. *Biomolecules*. 2022;12(4):589.
26. Taylor H, Barua N, Bienemann A, Wyatt M, Castrique E, Foster R, et al. Clearance and toxicity of recombinant methionyl human glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor (r-metHu GDNF) following acute convection-enhanced delivery into the striatum. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(3):e56186.
27. Akil O, Blits B, Lustig LR, Leake PA. Virally mediated overexpression of glial-derived neurotrophic factor elicits age- and dose-dependent neuronal toxicity and hearing loss. *Hum Gene Ther*. 2019;30(1):88-105.
28. Hovland DN, Jr., Boyd RB, Butt MT, Engelhardt JA, Moxness MS, Ma MH, et al. Six-month continuous intraputamenal infusion toxicity study of recombinant methionyl human glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor (r-metHuGDNF) in rhesus monkeys. *Toxicol Pathol*. 2007;35(7):1013-29.
29. Li Z, Gao Z, Sun T, Zhang S, Yang S, Zheng M, et al. Meteorin-like/Metrnl, a novel secreted protein implicated in inflammation, immunology, and metabolism: A comprehensive review of preclinical and clinical studies. *Frontiers in immunology*. 2023;14:1098570.
30. Whitlon D, Ketels K, Coulson M, Williams T, Grover M, Edpao W, et al. Survival and morphology of auditory neurons in dissociated cultures of newborn mouse spiral ganglion. *Neuroscience*. 2006;138(2):653-62.
31. Liu W, Edin F, Atturo F, Rieger G, Löwenheim H, Senn P, et al. The pre- and post-somatic segments of the human type I spiral ganglion neurons—structural and functional considerations related to cochlear implantation. *Neuroscience*. 2015;284:470-82.
32. Nayagam BA, Muniak MA, Ryugo DK. The spiral ganglion: connecting the peripheral and central auditory systems. *Hearing research*. 2011;278(1-2):2-20.
33. Coate TM, Kelley MW, editors. Making connections in the inner ear: recent insights into the development of spiral ganglion neurons and their connectivity with sensory hair cells. In *Seminars in cell & developmental biology* 2013 May 1 (Vol. 24, No. 5, pp. 460-469). Academic Press.
34. Lenarz T. Cochlear implant—state of the art. *Laryngo-rhino-otologie*. 2017;96(S 01):S123-S51.
35. Xie J, Pak K, Evans A, Kamgar-Parsi A, Fausti S, Mullen L, et al. Neurotrophins differentially stimulate the growth of cochlear neurites on collagen surfaces and in gels. *Neural regeneration research*. 2013;8(17):1541.
36. Leake PA, Rebscher SJ, Dore ' C, Akil O. AAV-mediated neurotrophin gene therapy promotes improved survival of cochlear spiral ganglion neurons in neonatally deafened cats: comparison of AAV2-hBDNF and AAV5-hGDNF. *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology*. 2019;20:341-61.

37. Schwieger J, Hamm A, Gepp MM, Schulz A, Hoffmann A, Lenarz T, et al. Alginate-encapsulated brain-derived neurotrophic factor–overexpressing mesenchymal stem cells are a promising drug delivery system for protection of auditory neurons. *Journal of tissue engineering*. 2020;11:2041731420911313.
38. Gillespie LN, Clark GM, Bartlett PF, Marzella PL. LIF is more potent than BDNF in promoting neurite outgrowth of mammalian auditory neurons in vitro. *Neuroreport*. 2001;12(2):275-9.
39. Jin Y, Kondo K, Ushio M, Kaga K, Ryan AF, Yamasoba T. Developmental changes in the responsiveness of rat spiral ganglion neurons to neurotrophic factors in dissociated culture: differential responses for survival, neuritogenesis and neuronal morphology. *Cell and tissue research*. 2013;351:15-27.
40. Hartnick C, Staecker H, Malgrange B, Lefebvre P, Liu W, Moonen G, et al. Neurotrophic effects of BDNF and CNTF, alone and in combination, on postnatal day 5 rat acoustic ganglion neurons. *Journal of neurobiology*. 1996;30(2):246-54.
41. Whitlon DS. Drug discovery for hearing loss: Phenotypic screening of chemical compounds on primary cultures of the spiral ganglion. *Hearing research*. 2017;349:177-81.
42. Kawano A, Seldon H, Clark G, Ramsden R, Raine C. Intracochlear factors contributing to psychophysical percepts following cochlear implantation. *Acta Otolaryngol*. 1998;118(3):313-26.
43. R&D Systems (2023a) [Internet]. Recombinant human Meteorin-like/METRNL protein. Available at: https://www.rndsystems.com/products/recombinant-human-meteorin-like-metrnl-protein-cf_9339-mn#product-Datasheets (Accessed May 15, 2023).

Figure Legends

Fig. 1. Examples of neurite outgrowth analysis of one SGE cultured in NOC: The explant's outline was marked (**a**, yellow line) to measure the explant area. To assess the neurite number, neurites growing out from the explant were counted manually (**b**, numbers around the SGE outline). For each SGE the length of the 10 longest neurites was measured using the polygon function (**c**, yellow line) to examine the neurite length. The area of outgrowing neurites was marked (yellow line) in relation to the position of the factor-releasing pump (left side of the image, not visible): facing towards the tube outlet (**d**) or away from it (**e**). All images display the same SGE in different magnifications, scale bar included in (**e**): 200 μm .

Fig. 2. Timeline of the different sample collection and time points during the two weeks of drug delivery by osmotic pumps.

Fig. 3. SGN culture using 10, 25, or 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin. Neurons are ANF-DAB stained and appear dark brown. After 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin-treatment, SGN exhibit normal appearance with visible neurites (indicated by white arrows). When adding 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin, the SGN number is massively reduced and no neurites are outgrowing. Using 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin, neurons and surrounding cells are rounded, detached and clustered. Scale bars: 50 μm .

Fig. 4. Neuronal survival of high dose group hCometin experiments: Mean and SD of the SGN survival rate (**a**) and number of neurons per well (**b**) of the different conditions. Addition of 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin to SGN resulted in neurotoxicity. Using 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ hCometin significantly protected neurons from degeneration compared to the negative control (NC) and the routinely used positive control (PC) with 50 ng/ml BDNF. Asterisks above the error

bars depict the significance of the condition compared to the respective condition marked by the arrowhead. (** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; independent experiments: 3, wells per experiment: 3)

Fig. 5. Morphology of SGN in high dose group hCometin experiments: (a) to (e) shows nominal statistics. Comparing negative (NC) and positive control (PC), the proportion of monopolar and bipolar neurons was significantly higher for PC-treatment with 50 ng/ml BDNF than in the untreated NC. In the case of the other morphologies, there was no difference between PC and NC. The addition of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin resulted in significantly more monopolar, bipolar, pseudomonopolar and, compared to PC, multipolar neurons than the other experimental conditions. Due to reduced survival and neurite regeneration after treatment with 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin, SGN morphology (with the exception of no neurites for 25 mg/ml hCometin) could not be assessed and is set to 0 in the graphs. These two conditions are excluded from statistics with the exception of neurons presenting no neurites. (f) presents the percentage of the neuronal morphologies in the different conditions and emphasizes the distinct increase in especially bipolar and monopolar neurons after treatment with 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin when compared to both controls. Asterisks above the error bars depict the significance of the condition compared to the respective condition marked by the arrowhead. (not significant: ns, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$; independent experiments: 3, wells per experiment: 3).

Fig. 6. Neuronal survival of medium dose group hCometin experiments: Neuronal survival rate (a) and number of neurons per well (b) were significantly improved compared to NC by PC with 50 ng/ml BDNF and the medium concentrations of 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin. The effect of hCometin did not differ from that of BDNF, although the means were higher for 10 and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin. Asterisks above the error bars depict the significance of the condition compared to the respective condition marked by the arrowhead. (** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$; independent experiments: 4; wells per experiment: 3)

Fig. 7. SGN morphology of medium dose group hCometin experiments: Graphs (a) to (e) show the number of counted SGN of the different morphologies for medium doses of human hCometin compared to negative (NC) and positive control (PC, 50 ng/ml BDNF). Neuronal morphology was positively influenced by treatment with the medium concentrations of hCometin with higher numbers of neurons regenerating neurites and lower numbers of neurons without neurites. The increase in number of monopolar and bipolar SGN was superior for 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin when compared to NC and PC. In addition, the number of pseudomonopolar and multipolar neurons was significantly increased compared to NC and PC, and number of neurons without neurites was significantly reduced compared to PC by treatment with 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin. For comparative purposes (f) presents the percentage of the neuronal morphologies in the different conditions in a stacked bar format. The graph visualizes the increase of neurons with regenerated neurites, especially of monopolar and bipolar neurons, with increasing concentration of hCometin and in comparison to the controls. Asterisks above the error bars depict the significance of the condition compared to the respective condition marked by the arrowhead. (** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns: not significant; independent experiments: 4, wells per experiment: 3)

Fig. 8. Measured neurite length of medium dose group hCometin treated SGN: The mean neurite length was significantly increased by the PC including 50 ng/ml BDNF and by 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as well as 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin when compared to the NC. 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin performed as good as BDNF, which was not the case for 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ hCometin. Asterisks above the error bars depict the significance of the condition compared to the respective condition marked by the arrowhead. (** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns: not significant; independent experiments: 4, wells per experiment: 3)

Fig. 9. Neurite outgrowth in NOC experiments: The underlying area of SGE (a) was measured as the basis for neurite outgrowth and did not differ significantly between NOCs treated with AP-only (NC) or with hCometin by mini-osmotic pump delivery for five days. Neither the number of neurites per SGE (b) nor the neurite number calculated in consideration of the SGE area (neurites normalized to mm^2 SGE) (c) differed significantly between NC and hCometin. However, length of neurites cultured with hCometin infusion was significantly shorter than the length of NC neurites (d), while this was not the case for the neurite coverage area (e), which was determined by marking the outline of the outgrown neurites and subtracting the respective SGE area. (Asterisks above the line depict the detected significance *** $p < 0.001$, ns: not significant; Number of NOC analysed: 12, 6 NC and 6 Cometin)

Fig. 10. Neurite orientation in NOC experiments: Percentage of number of neurites growing towards (+) or away (-) from the connection channel (a) and percentage of neurite coverage area (b) of each direction in NC and hCometin groups. There was no significant difference in percentage terms between NC and hCometin for number

of neurites and neurite covered area regarding the orientation. (ns: not significant; Number of NOC analysed: 12, 6 NC and 6 Cometin)

Fig. 11. Overview of hCometin concentrations in pump-based infused NOCs detected by ELISA at the different time points of collection: Purple and magenta bars show the measured concentration of hCometin ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) when reconstituted in AP (pure I and II) to a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$ for subsequent filling of the osmotic pumps. The supernatants of NOCs were analysed over two distinct two-week cycles (I and II), which are separated by a dashed line. Blue bars represent the results for the preincubation (pre1d) and interim collections in PBS (each $500 \mu\text{l}$, pre: 1 day, interim: 2 days of delivery) while the green bars show the results of the NOC medium supernatants (each $150 \mu\text{l}$, 5 days delivery). Note that supernatants from the first five days of NOC delivery in the first pumping cycle (I Com1 and 2 1-5d) were lost due to leakage and are not included in the graph. Overall, the detected hCometin concentration was higher in the first cycle and decreased over time. However, the pure hCometin solution used for pump filling had a much lower concentration (31 and $25 \mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively) than the targeted $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. During preincubation, very low amounts of $\sim 500 - 50 \text{ pg/ml}$ or no hCometin were measured. At the end of the NOC experiments, concentrations of about $3.4 \mu\text{g/ml}$ second NOCs, first cycle, $3 \mu\text{g/ml}$ first NOCs, second cycle, and $1.3 \mu\text{g/ml}$ second NOCs, second cycle were detected. In the interim collections, hCometin concentration was lower overall and dropped from $0.04 - 0.07 \mu\text{g/ml}$ at the first cycle to $0.007 \mu\text{g/ml}$ at the end of the second cycle. Data given as mean \pm SD in $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

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Table 1: Overview of the collected and ELISA-analysed samples

	Preincubation 24h	NOC 1-5d	Interim collection 6/7d	NOC 8-12d	Interim collection 13/14d	hCometin solution in AP	Inner ear tissue supernatant (48h cultivation)
Pumping cycle I	I Com1, I Com2, I NC1, I NC2		I Com1, I Com2, I NC1, I NC2	I Com1, I Com2, I NC1, I NC2	I Com1, I Com2, I NC1, I NC2	pure I	spiral ganglion; organ of Corti; organ of Corti with attached SG
Pumping cycle II	II Com1, II Com2, II NC1, II NC2	II Com1, II Com2, II NC1, II NC2	II Com1, II Com2, II NC1, II NC2	II Com1, II Com2, II NC1, II NC2	II Com1, II Com2, II NC1, II NC2	pure II	
N =	8	4	8	8	8	2	3

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of number and percentage of SGN morphologies in high dose Cometin experiments

	NC		PC (BDNF)		hCometin 10		hCometin 25		hCometin 50	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Monopolar	14.78 ± 4.17	21.44 ± 8.89	40.67 ± 2.31	31.81 ± 8.14	70.56 ± 10.78	50.86 ± 7.87	0	0	0	0
Pseudo-monopolar	0.11 ± 0.19	0.44 ± 1.33	0.33 ± 0	0.28 ± 0.42	1.56 ± 0.69	1.14 ± 0.41	0	0	0	0
Bipolar	1.78 ± 0.19	3.18 ± 2.36	6.44 ± 2.91	5.12 ± 2.51	20.44 ± 2.22	14.91 ± 3.01	0	0	0	0
Multipolar	0.22 ± 0.19	0.25 ± 0.50	0	0	1.00 ± 0.58	0.68 ± 1.02	0	0	0	0
No neurites	58.33 ± 31.82	74.68 ± 10.60	78.56 ± 9.71	62.79 ± 7.92	42.78 ± 9.35	32.41 ± 9.05	34.11 ± 19.91	100	0	0

Table 3. Mean \pm Standard Deviation of number and percentage of SGN morphologies in medium dose Cometin experiments

	NC		PC (BDNF)		hCometin 10		hCometin 25		hCometin 50	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Monopolar	27.83 \pm 14,34	19.70 \pm 7.72	68.42 \pm 25.69	34.26 \pm 10.45	60.83 \pm 15.94	34.52 \pm 4.76	76.92 \pm 22.44	39.05 \pm 5.44	72.42 \pm 15.11	38.89 \pm 4.46
Pseudo-monopolar	0.42 \pm 0.79	0.25 \pm 0.47	0.92 \pm 0.79	0.47 \pm 0.42	1.67 \pm 0.98	0.96 \pm 0.68	1.17 \pm 1.19	0.57 \pm 0.65	2.75 \pm 1.66	1.47 \pm 0.90
Bipolar	3.08 \pm 2.61	2.06 \pm 1.75	13.67 \pm 8.14	6.78 \pm 3.67	14.42 \pm 3.55	8.44 \pm 2.74	24.33 \pm 5.45	12.63 \pm 2.16	28 \pm 9.70	15.03 \pm 3.87
Multipolar	0.33 \pm 0.65	0.21 \pm 0.44	0.75 \pm 0.97	0.36 \pm 0.45	0.92 \pm 1.08	0.54 \pm 1.09	2.08 \pm 1.98	1.05 \pm 1.07	2.92 \pm 2.64	1.52 \pm 1.24
No neurites	105.8 \pm 30.41	77.78 \pm 8.11	113.6 \pm 28.41	58.13 \pm 14.11	97.92 \pm 24.68	55.54 \pm 5.43	91.25 \pm 20.37	46.70 \pm 5.79	82.08 \pm 25.41	43.08 \pm 6.30